

International Journal of Research in Management Fields

Available online on

<http://rspublication.com/IJRES/IJRE.html>

ISSN:(P) 2572-4274 (O) 2572-4304

ARTICLE INFO

©2026 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJRMF-

69D7FD27AA5A12

Published: 2026-04-23

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/>

zenodo.19705140

Page No:12/1-12/11

A STUDY ON FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG STUDENTS

Dr. RAGA JYOTHI. L¹, KRISHNA BIJU², RITHVIK P³

Asst. Professor¹, Student², Student³

S.E.A College of Science, Commerce and Arts, Autonomous, Bangalore

✉ ragajyothi.seacollege@gmail.com¹, ✉ krishnabiju48@gmail.com²,

✉ rithvik87590@gmail.com³

ABSTRACT

Financial literacy among students in India has given a very important priority, the financial literacy is the process of managing money and students will get to know how to manage money and students will get know how to manage money, generate income, savings, investment and also to spend money after using for all of his expenses and expenditure. This study helps students to know the importance of managing money which will help our country and economy to gain knowledge of utilizing money and saving the money. The information was gathered by collecting primary data with the help of questionnaire and also secondary data. The study of financial literacy among students can be concluded that improving financial knowledge among student is very important for their future to make better financial decision and to achieve their success and their goals. In conclusion, financial literacy helps students understand how to manage money properly. It teaches them the importance of saving, spending wisely, and making good financial. Therefore, improving financial knowledge among students is very important for their future.

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, money plays an important role in everyone's life, especially for students. Financial literacy means having the knowledge and skills to manage money wisely. It includes understanding how to earn, save, spend, borrow, and invest money responsibly so that one can build a secure future.

For many students, college or university is the first time they handle money independently. While this independence is exciting, it also brings responsibility. Students must manage tuition fees, rent, food, transportation, books, and other personal expenses. Some work part-time jobs, while others depend on family support or student loans without proper financial knowledge, managing these responsibilities can become stressful.

Mobile banking apps, online shopping, digital wallets, and buy-now-pay-later services allow easy access to money. However, this convenience can encourage unnecessary spending. Quick online payments often reduce awareness of how much money is being spent.

Financial stability, on the other hand, allows students to focus better on their academic goals and personal growth. Improving financial literacy among students is therefore essential. Students should take personal responsibility for learning how to manage money and make better decisions in future about money management to achieve their success in their life and to be financial independent in their future.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Bawalle and Chawla (2025) Conducted a study on financial literacy among students and found that students with high financial overconfidence especially those using mobile payment apps are far more likely to take on high-cost debt like payday loans. Students who are overconfident about their financial knowledge even if they don't actually possess strong financial literacy are more likely to engage in harmful financial decisions, especially when eased by mobile payment technology. This suggests that having knowledge alone does not prevent and sometime increases risk taking in students and make students to take loan and students will be unable to pay loan and fall in debt and make students more stressful with more financial confidence.

2. Shailendra Kumar Shukla and Dr. Meenakshi Singh (2024) examined a study on financial literacy around the world. The study emphasized that the financial literacy is essential for making better decisions regarding the monetary which leads to a good financial stability and improve the quality of life of students as well as an individual. Financial literacy enables individuals and students to make informed financial decisions regarding the saving, investing, budgeting and plan for the future to secure financial stability. The researchers highlighted financial literacy is important for

everyone including students, youth, investors it is important for them to make better financial decisions so that they can achieve a good financial stability and achieve their goals and desires.

3.S. Veena, M. Sharon Arpana and T.R. Bharath (2023) analyzed a study on financial literacy among college students at the school of Management Hindustan Institute of Technology and Science. The study emphasized that the financial literacy has become essential due to the increasing complexity of financial products and services. The researchers highlighted that the financial literacy involves knowledge of money management, savings, investment and credit and also examined how demographic characteristics related to the financial literacy in students and how well students understand and apply financial knowledge in real life which are crucial for making informed financial decisions and ensure long term financial stability and success

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is the specific procedures or techniques used to identify, select, process and analyze information about the topic. It is a way of systematically solving the research problems. For the purpose of this study a random sampling method was followed and 50 responses were collected. The study uses questionnaire method of data collection.

1.RESEARCH DESIGN: The study of financial literacy among students is done through quantitative research by collecting response from the questionnaire and measure the level of financial literacy through data analysis and interpretation.

2.RESEARCH TYPE: The study of financial literacy among students has adopted a descriptive research where it describes the present level of financial literacy among students and to understand the level and awareness of financial literacy among students.

3. Data collection Method: The study of financial literacy among students is collected from primary data and secondary. The primary data is collected through questionnaires and Google form responses and secondary data is collected through the articles which is published in journals.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the financial literacy among students.
2. To understand various alternatives in financial literacy among students.
3. To suggest measures for improving financial literacy among students.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Responses may be biased and has limited sample size.
2. Lack of financial knowledge among respondents.
3. Lack of planning and interesting about financial literacy.
4. Lack of money management among students.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTREPRETATION

1. Analysis on Gender

Interpretation: It was observed that 52% of respondents are female and 48% of respondents are male.

2. Awareness of How financial literacy will help students

Interpretation: It was found that 64% of respondents are able to make informed financial decisions,18% of the respondents will teach how to spend money quickly,14% of respondents will focus only on earning money and 4% of respondents encourage them to borrow more money. Most of the respondents believe financial literacy helps students by teaching them how to make informed financial decisions.

3.Respondents view on the primary purpose of financial literacy

Interpretation: It is viewed that 84% of the respondents were able to understand and manage personal finances effectively ,10% of the respondents were able to earn as much money possible,4% of the respondents learned how to trade stocks daily and 2% of respondents were able to spend more money and the majority of respondents believe the primary purpose of financial literacy is to understand and manage personal finance effectively.

Analysis on the benefit of being financially literate

Interpretation: It has been analyzed that 66% of the respondents were able to reduce debt, increase savings and improves financial stability,28% of the respondents were able to plan for the future and 6% of the respondents have increased financial stress. Most respondents believe that being financially literate helps to reduce debt, increase savings and improve financial stability.

5. Awareness on why saving money important according to financial literacy principle

Interpretation: It has been found that 86% of the respondents have money for future emergencies and needs,10 % of the respondents were able to buy unnecessary items, 2% of the respondents were able to borrow money and 2 % of respondents were able to lend money to friends and large majority of respondents understand the primary principle of saving money is to prepare for future emergencies and needs.

6.Respondents view on what is the best way to start becoming financially literate

Interpretation: It has been viewed that 70% of the respondents are able to understand basic money concept, 22% of the respondents are able to follow trusted financial sources, 6% of the respondents are able to save fund from more sales and 2% of the respondents are agreed for none of the above and A significant majority of respondents believe that understanding basic money concept is the best way to begin the journey toward financial literacy.

7. Analysis on how financial literacy help students to avoid

Interpretation: It has been analyzed that 72% of the respondents avoid unnecessary debt, 14% of the respondents agree for financial independence, 10% of the respondents agreed for smart

investments and 4% of the respondents agreed for none of the above and the response show that a strong consensus among respondents that the primary benefit of financial literacy for students is helping them to avoid unnecessary debt.

8.Awareness on why it is important for students to track their expenses

Interpretation: It has been observed that 94 % of the respondents avoid overspending, 4% of the respondents are comparing with friends,2% of the respondents are spending more money and majority of students track their expenses primarily avoid overspending indicating this is the most important concern for them.

9. Respondents view on which of the following is a good financial habit.

Interpretation: It has been viewed that 88% of the respondents are comparing prices before purchasing goods ,6 % of the respondents adopted for impulse buying,4% of the respondents are found spending all pocket money at once and 2 % of the respondents are ignoring savings and the respondents correctly considers comparing prices before purchasing to be a good financial habit.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. Most respondents believe that financial literacy helps students by teaching them how to make informed financial decisions.
2. The majority of respondents believe that the primary purpose of financial literacy is to understand and manage personal finance effectively.
3. Most respondents believe that being financially literate helps to reduce debt, increase savings and improve financial stability.
4. Large majority of respondents understand the primary principle of saving money is to prepare for future emergencies and needs.
5. A significant majority of respondents believe that understanding basic money concept is the best way to begin the journey towards financial literacy.
6. The response show that a strong consensus among respondents that the primary benefits of financial literacy for students is helping them to avoid unnecessary debt.
7. Majority of students track their expenses primarily to avoid overspending, indicating this the most important concern for them.
8. The respondents correctly consider comparing prices before purchasing to be a good financial habit.

SUGGESTIONS OF THE STUDY

1. School, Colleges and Universities should incorporate financial literacy into their core curriculum so the students understand the importance of financial literacy and able to save money for future needs.

2. Organize regular financial literacy program and workshops for the students so that students became aware and start better planning to manage their finances for their future.

3. Use social media platforms to share reliable financial literacy information among students so that students become aware and start to make better decisions for the future.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

Financial literacy is important for students to manage personal finance, debt and how to achieve success in their financial planning and decisions to ensure long term financial stability. Educational institutions should sufficiently equip students with practical financial skills and knowledge to achieve success in their financial stability. The study of financial literacy among students emphasizes that inadequate financial literacy can lead to poor financial decisions, increased debt, lack of savings, and financial insecurity in students. Therefore, integrating structured financial education programs into school and university curriculum is essential to equip students with the knowledge and skills required for responsible financial behavior. Improving financial literacy among students is not only beneficial for individual financial well-being but also crucial for broader economic stability and growth. Educational institutions, policymakers, and families must collaborate to promote financial awareness and empower students to make informed financial decisions throughout their lives. The overall study suggests that financial literacy plays a very important role in shaping responsible financial attitudes among students. It helps them build stability, avoid financial stress, and prepare for a secure future.

REFERENCE

1. Lovekesh.L and Kumar, (2025). understanding *the study on financial literacy among the students*.

2. Jacob.MS, (2024). *financial literacy among the students*.

3. Vaghela.P. S and Patil. A. G, (2023). *the effect of financial literacy and attitude on financial behaviour among students*.

4. Nandi.S and Kolhe. V, (2022). *awareness on a study of financial literacy among students*.

- 5.Priyadarshini. S and Kumari. J, (2021).** *analysing a study on financial literacy among students.*

- 6.Hairunnizam Wahid and Aisyah Zahari, (2020).** *published a study on financial literacy among students.*

- 7. T. Sakiridou. H and Seitanidis, (2019).** *have done a study on financial literacy among students and indicate the financial literacy level among students.*

- 8.Garg.N and Singh. S, (2018).** *researched a study on financial literacy among students it indicates the issues faced in financial literacy among students.*

- 9.Ergun.K, (2017).** *examined a study on financial literacy among students.*

- 10.Kiliyanni. A and Sivaraman. S, (2016).** *has researched a study on financial literacy among the student.*